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PHRASES, EXPRESSIONS AND COLLOCATIONS USING “TRAVEL”, “HOLIDAY” AND “TOURISM” WORDS USED IN TRAVELLING AND TOURISM

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Abstract. This study focuses on the words “travel”, “holiday” and “tourism” and their collocations and expressions so that students can use these important terms flexibly. In order to meet the communicative demands of the tourism industry our learners need proficient levels of general language skills. Tourism has been diversified, therefore sun and sand are no longer being the only option available, from rural tourism to adventure holidays and including ecotourism which is very related to the environment. The Travel and Tourism students need to be aware of currently used specialised vocabulary in their field of studies. Vocabulary learning is an essential part in foreign language learning, as the meanings of new words are not familiar to students or learners. Linguistic research in this field has mainly focused on the linguistic features of mediated representations such as brochures, websites and guidebooks. Lexical knowledge is central to communicative competence and to acquisition of a second foreign language and a lack of vocabulary knowledge is an obstacle to learning. Having these goals as background the paper wants to develop a practical direction. It is meant to be a useful tool for students and teachers of English, both at university level and for English as a second language, as well as for anyone interested in the specialised vocabulary used in travelling and tourism.

Keywords: *communication approach, cultural diversity, flexible terms, specialised vocabulary, travel buzzwords.*

Introduction

Tourism is a multiple faceted phenomenon which in contemporary societies represents one of the most important elements of cultural interaction based on the circulation of people and information. The aim of language in tourism contexts is “to convert people description and visual elements¹”. The present study aims to investigate the phraseology of tourism, i.e lexical choices and recurring patterns. The data are extracted from a corpus amounting to 2,000 words by reading, consulting and downloading the pages of various touristic sites, British newspapers and magazines or various hotel sites. The United Nations World Tourism Organization defines tourism” as any activity that occurs when tourists travel, which encompasses everything from the planning the trip, travelling to the place, the staying itself, returning and reminiscences”.

¹ Dann Graham, 2002, - The Tourist as a Metaphor of the Social World, Wallingford: CAB International. p.89

Regarding the definition of “collocation” Cruse² uses the term to refer to strings of lexical items that occur together, exhibit a preference for each other but he adds that these lexical items are „fully transparent” in the sense that each lexical constituent is also a semantic constituent. Cowie³ contrasts collocations to idioms which are interchangeable and whose parts cannot be substituted or expanded in any way. Taking into account all these the article has two directions: to provide a selection of the most commonly used phrases, expressions and collocations in tourism and travelling and to offer guidance on the most effective way to use them.

Travel buzzwords

Buzzwords are words or phrases from one special area of knowledge that people think it is very important. Such words related to travel and tourism can include:

Wellnes travel- travelling for promoting health and well-being through physical, psychological or spiritual activities

Hipster holiday- which follows the latest trends and fashions, especially those outside the cultural mainstream

Cultural travel/tourism- sightseeing or visiting museums to learn about history, art and people’s lifestyles

Recreational tourism- when tourists want to relax and have fun, maybe at the beach

Adventure tourism- to explore distant places or do extreme activities

Mystery travel- a trip that is organized like an interactive game, with riddles that unlock planned activities when they are solved

Ecotourism- going on holiday to places of natural beauty in a way that causes less damage to the environment

Travel agency- is a private retailer or public service that provides travel and tourism related services to the public on behalf of suppliers such as activities, airlines, car rentals, cruise lines, hotels, railways, travel insurance, and package tours

Tourism trend- the general tendency in tourism/travelling

Travel services- activities, airlines, car rentals, cruise lines, hotels, railways, travel insurance

Travel alert- a travel warning, travel alert, or travel advisory is an official warning statement issued by a government agency to provide information about the relative safety of travelling to or visiting one or more specific foreign countries or destinations.

Travel collocations

- hordes/ thongs of *travellers*- a lot of tourists to *travel* cheap- without spending a lot of money
- every *traveller’s* playground- a place where a particular group of people enjoy themselves
- independent *travel*- not travelling in a group/ confident and able to do things by himself
- to *travel* with a crowd- to travel in a group
- budget *travel*- with little money to spend
- *travel* photo addiction- the strong desire of taking photos during a holiday
- frugal *travel*- a budget travel with little money to spend
- *travel*-sized items- items which are designed to be suitable for travelling

² Cruse David, 1986, *Lexical Semantics*, Cambridge University Press, p.41

³ Cowie Anthony- *Phraseology. Theory, analysis, and applications*. Oxford Studies in Lexicography and Lexicology. Oxford: Oxford University Press

- pesky *travellers*- annoying travellers
- *travel* tote- to carry something regularly during a trip
- *travellers* yearning (for)- travellers who have a strong desire to do something
- picky *traveller*- someone who is not easy to please
- *travel* bug- strong desire to travel
- to *travel* by stages- travelling only a short distance at a time
- price consciouns *traveller*- a traveller who doesn't want to spend too much money
- *traveler's* reviews- traveller's opinions about
- *to travel* light- without taking a lot of luggage
- time-crunchers *travelers*- travelers who have to travel a lot in a short period of time
- *travel* hacks- shared experiences that will have your travel experiences easier and more enjoyable
- savvy *travelers*- who are clever and know how to handle with situations successfully
- culture-hungry *traveller*—somebody who is interested to know a lot about the history of a place, for example
- *traveller's* convience- what is the easiest and the best for a traveller
- life-changing *travelling*- transformative, mind-blowing travelling
- *travel*-friendly- not difficult to use or understand
- long-haul *travel*- a long distance one
- *travelling* essentials- things necessary during a holiday
- wasteful/lavish *traveller*- who uses/ spends more money that he should
- pitfalls of *travelling*- problems, difficulties that is likely to happen during a holiday
- *travel*ocity- a popular internet search engine that displays airlines, hotel and rental cars fares from different companies simultaneously
- *travel* cheap- not spending so much money
- avid *traveller*- someone who travels as much as possible
- bleisure *travellers*- professionals who are refraining the all-work and no-fun kind of business trip by mixing them with vacation time
- go-to *travel* shoes- comfortable shoes
- on the radar of *travellers*- to draw the traveller's attention
- to *travel* on short notice- when you are told about it only a short time before it happens
- outbound *travel*- a travel that implies moving away from a town/ a country
- desirable *travel* months- months that worth travelling
- *mystery travel*- a trip that is organised like an interactive game with riddles that unlock planned activities when they are solved
- *overland travel*- self-realiant to remote destionations where the journey is the principal goal
- arduous *travel*- difficult/tiring trip
- intrepid *traveller*- brave, with no fear of dangerous situations

Tourism collocations

- tombstone *tourism*- visiting famous people's tombstones
- cradle of *tourism*- the place where something important has begun
- strain of *tourism*- a particular quality which tourism has
- to draw *tourists* to- to bring tourists to
- *touristry*- a place that is full of tourists and full of things that attract tourists (used to show dissapproval)

- *tourist-class*- the cheapest standard of travelling conditions on a plane in a ship
- *tourism dropping*- to fall to a lower level
- *tourist trap*- a place that many tourists visit where drinks, hotels, etc are very expensive
- *dark tourism*- focused on places where tragic events have occurred

Holiday collocations

- *holiday-worthy places*- places that a value in money
- the buzz of the *holiday*- the excitement of the upcoming holiday
- *holiday shaming*- work environments where colleagues and bosses indirectly discourage employees from taking time off
- *carefree holiday*- having no problems or worries
- to *holidaying*- to travel
- *smooth holiday*- very pleasant, without any unpleasant moment
- *holiday treat*- something special
- *regular holidays*- to travel regularly
- *holiday philosophy*- the attitude/ set of ideas that guides the behaviour of a person
- *holiday heaven*- a real heaven, a suitable place
- *busman's holiday*- a holiday in which somebody is doing the same thing he does when he works
- *upcoming holiday*- next holiday
- *disconnecting holiday*- leaving all computers and devices at home
- *holidaymakers*- someone who has travelled to a place on a holiday
- *holiday-worthy spots*- spots that worth visiting while you are on holiday
- to have *holiday days* (on the table)- to have unused free days

Conclusion

The tourist sector has witnessed a drastic transformation in the past few years. Until a few decades ago, tourism was mainly a privileged activity for the "happy few" or a period of relaxation during a few weeks a year for the population at large. The vocabulary used in tourism becomes a vector of knowledge which promotes linguistic and cultural diversity. This paper aims to offer an appetite of this fascinating vocabulary used in this domain. People who work in the travel industry around the world generally use English as a common language to communicate with international tourists. This not only includes tour guides, but also people working in hotels, restaurants, transportation services and more. You could work in a bakery in a busy tourist district, as a taxi driver, a hotel receptionist or even a bike tour guide. Because there are so many jobs in tourism, there are many different types of tourism English. If you are looking at a job in this dynamic, international industry, you will discover that your daily responsibilities require a special set of vocabulary.

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